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Measuring the associations between smartphone use and subjective well-being during normal use and a deprivation condition:

A hybrid feedback and elicitation diary combined with a qualitative interview guideline

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Description of the instruments:

The three instruments were applied in a qualitative prolonged, quasi-experimental deprivation study using a mixed-methods design.

The aim of this study was to measure the associations between smartphone use (in particular functions and situations) and subjective well-being (in particular emotions, day satisfaction and satisfaction with social contacts).

The study was partitioned into three phases: During the first phase (5 days), the participants' smartphone use was monitored under normal conditions. During the second phase (5 days), the participants were not allowed to use their smartphones (the deprivation phase). In phase 3, a qualitative interview was conducted. Phase 3 followed the deprivation phase immediately.

- **Instrument 1: Situational questionnaire (phase 1 and phase 2):** Measures associations between specific situations (where?) and functions (what did you do?) of smartphone use and the emotions (=affective component of subjective well-being). Phase 1 refers to normal usage phase/ phase 2 refers to the deprivation condition. Needs to be filled out 4 times a day.
- **Instrument 2: Daily questionnaire (phase 1 and phase 2):** Measures the cognitive component of subjective well-being, namely general satisfaction with the current day and domain satisfaction with the social relations. Phase 1 refers to normal usage phase/ phase 2 refers to the deprivation condition. Needs to be filled out once a day (in the evening).
- **Instrument 3: Qualitative interview guideline (phase 3):** Measures subjective interpretations of the findings obtained with instrument 1 and 2 as well as general experiences during deprivation.

Phase 1 and 2: Day [1 to 10]: Time [11 am/2 pm/5 pm/9 pm]*

*Four questionnaires each day.

Instrument 1: Situational Questionnaire

(Phase 1: normal use / Phase 2: deprivation condition)¹

Phase 1: Where did you use your smartphone?

Phase 2: Where would you have liked to use your smartphone?

- at home
 - at work
 - at school/university
 - in a café or restaurant
 - while doing sports
 - in bus/train/subway
 - while driving in a car
 - while being with friends/family
 - in a store
 - while waiting
 - in other situations:
-

Phase 1: What did you do with your smartphone?

Phase 2: What would you have liked to do with your smartphone?

- chatting
 - social networking
 - news-/infotainment
 - multimedia
 - organization
 - navigation/travelling
 - working
 - gaming or learning
 - shopping
 - for nothing specific
 - for other reasons:
-

Phase: 1 How did you feel when using your smartphone? (multiple answers possible)²

Phase: 2: How did you feel when not being able to use your smartphone? (multiple answers possible)²

- annoyed relaxed stressed activ
 - interested enthusiastic calm happy
 - inspired irritated nervous bored
 - ashamed frustrated concerned entertained
 - I had no emotions.
 - Other: _____
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¹ The instruments have been translated from German into English by the authors.

² Adapted from the Positive and Negative Effect Schedule (PANAS; Crawford & Henry, 2004)

Phase 1 and 2: Day [1 to 10]: Time [11 am/2 pm/5 pm/9 pm]*

*Four questionnaires each day.

Note (*Phase 1: What have you done with your smartphone? Why did you have this/these emotion/s? Why did you use a specific application? Phase 2: What did you want to do with your smartphone? Why did you have this/these emotion/s? Why did you want to use a specific application?*)

Phase 1 and 2: Day [1 to 10]*

*One questionnaire a day.

Instrument 2: Daily Questionnaire

(Phase 1: normal use/ Phase 2: deprivation condition)

Please remember how satisfied have you been today with...³

(1=not satisfied to 5=satisfied)

	1	2	3	4	5
the day in general	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
your social contacts	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]

With how many friends, acquaintances, relatives and colleagues have you been in contact today?

I had contact with _____ persons.

Did you take part in social activities apart from work/university/school?

[] Yes, I had a unique meeting

[] Yes, I had a regular meeting

[] No

Please remember: Which were the last three persons you have been in contact with and what kind of device did you use?

I had contact to...

[] a family member

[] my life partner

[] a friend

[] an acquaintance

[] a colleague

[] to someone else:

I used...

[] a telephone

[] a computer

[] a mobile phone

[] a tablet

[] nothing (face2face)

[] something else:

³ Adapted from the Personal Well-Being Index (International Well-being Group, 2013)

Phase 1 and 2: Day [1 to 10]*

*One questionnaire a day.

If I used a computer, mobile phone, tablet or a similar digital device, the contact was via...

a chat application

a social network

an online-forum/game

something else:

(Hint: these questions were asked three times)

Note (*Why have you been satisfied/unsatisfied? What did you like most/least when being in contact with your social contacts?*)

Phase 3: After deprivation

Instrument 3: The Qualitative Interview
(phase 3, after deprivation)

Category	Question
Expectations	Why did you decide to take part in the study? What did you expect?
Smartphone Use	What do you personally think about your way of using the smartphone? <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ How often do you normally use your smartphone?○ How important is it for you?○ For what do you use your smartphone mostly?○ Where or when do you use it most often?
Subjective Well-Being by comparing smartphone use and deprivation	Tell me about situations in which you would have liked to use the smartphone during deprivation. <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ When did you want to use it and for what? Do you remember situations in which you were happy that you were not to be able to use your phone? <i>If yes, please tell me more about these situations?</i>○ Do you remember situations in which you would have been happier without the smartphone? <i>If yes, please tell me more about these situations?</i> How did your social contacts change without the smartphone? <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ How would you evaluate the change of social contacts?

Phase 3: After deprivation

	Did you felt more or less satisfied when not using your smartphone?	
Smartphone Deprivation	How hard was the deprivation for you? <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ What was particularly difficult?○ What was easier than expected?○ Have you ever considered interrupting the experiment?○ Comparing the beginning of the deprivation with the end: Did it become easier or more difficult to abstain from the smartphone?	
	Tell me about situations you would have liked to use the smartphone and in which you decided to so something else. <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ For what kind of alternatives did you decide?○ Did these alternatives fulfill their purpose?○ Have you done things you normally do not do?	
	How did the people in your environment react on your participation in the experiment? <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Are there people in your social circle who generally do not use a smartphone?○ How do people in your social circle evaluate your smartphone use? Do they criticize your behavior?○ Are there many people who expect you to have your smartphone with you?	

Phase 3: After deprivation

	All in all: Was it a good or a bad experience to abstain from your smartphone for a while? <i>If yes or no, why?</i> Could you imagine living without a smartphone? <i>If yes or no, why?</i>
Evaluation of the Experiment	Did you learn something from the experiment?

References

- Crawford, J. R., & Henry, J. D. (2004). The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS): Construct validity, measurement properties and normative data in a large non-clinical sample. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, (43), 245–265.
- International Wellbeing Group (2013). *Personal Wellbeing Index* (5th ed.). Melbourne: Australia: The Australian Centre on Quality of Life, Deakin University. Retrieved from: <http://www.deakin.edu.au/research/acqol/instruments/wellbeing-index/pwi-english.pdf>